

EAPR Pathology & Pests Section Meeting

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**Dealing with potato pathogens & pests in a context
of global change**

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Ecobreed: Evaluating wireworm (Coleoptera: Elateridae) control strategies in potato

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As part of the EU ECOBREED project, we tested different formulations based on the entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) *Metarhizium brunneum* and *Metarhizium robertsii* for wireworm control, and evaluated different fungal modes of action such as plant growth stimulation, bioaugmentation, and the »attract and kill« method. We set up two field experiments in 2020 and two in 2021, testing six *Metarhizium* isolates from the mycological collection of the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, which have been shown to be highly virulent in previous experiments, in three different formulations: (a) potato tubers soaked in the fungal suspension of all six isolates (potato + fungi), (b) fungi formulated on rice (potato + rice) and (c), a combination of both treatments (potato + fungi + rice). Two treatments with the commercial bioinsecticide Attracap (Biocare GmbH;) were tested at full and half doses, and the commercial insecticide Force (Syngenta, active ingredient Tefluthrin, 15 g/kg) was used as a conventional control treatment alongside the untreated control. The most effective fungal bioinsecticide in 2020 was half dose of Attracap, as it reduced the number of wireworm tunnels per tuber by 28.6 % and the proportion of damaged tubers by 12.8 % compared to the control. In 2021, the most effective fungal bioinsecticide was fungi formulated on rice as it reduced the number of tunnels per tuber by 39.5 % and the proportion of damaged tubers by 41.7 % compared to the control. However, in both years Force was the only treatment that significantly reduced the number of tunnels per individual tuber and the proportion of damaged tubers. Tuber yield showed no significant differences between treatments in either year. Nevertheless, the efficacy of the bioaugmentation method, in the form of fungi formulated on rice, was found to be comparable to commercial bioinsecticides and chemical insecticides in reducing the proportion of damaged tubers and the number of tunnels per potato tuber.

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Laboratory and field evaluation of bioinsecticides for Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) control

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Colorado potato beetle (CPB) is the most important insect defoliator of potatoes and can be controlled with insecticides based on plant extracts, entomopathogenic microorganisms and other substances that pose a low risk to human and animal health and the environment. Within the EU project ECOBREED (grant number 771367), laboratory and field trials were conducted in 2020 and 2021 to test four bioinsecticides (azadirachtin – product Neemazal, spinosad – Laser Plus, conidial suspension of two isolates of entomopathogenic fungus (EPF) *Beauveria bassiana*, *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *tenebrionis* (Btt) – Novodor) and RNA interference (RNAi) against CPB larvae. The EPF were also combined with different doses of azadirachtin and spinosad to explore potential synergistic interactions between treatments. Treatment efficacy was determined by CPB larval mortality and a decrease in potato leaf consumption. A mix of both EPF isolates outperformed individual isolates and, combined with a 2% recommended dose of spinosad or 100% dose of azadirachtin outperformed those bioinsecticides alone, in laboratory assays. In field experiments in both years, treatments with spinosad (full and 20% dose, and spinosad + EPF) and azadirachtin alone showed significant larval reduction. In contrast, EPF, Btt and RNAi did not significantly control CPB larvae. All treatments except EPF in both years and RNAi in 2021 significantly reduced defoliation of potato plants. Despite significant differences in defoliation and larval reduction observed on individual plants, no significant differences in tuber yield were observed between treated and untreated field experimental plots, after a single (bio)insecticide application.

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